

Ingliz tilini o'rganishda motivatsiyaning ahamiyati
Важность мотивации в изучении английского языка
The importance of Motivation in learning English

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Abstract: The learners' motivation is crucial when learning a language. Motivating EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students to participate in their learning is important. Some experts concur, according to Dornyei (1998), that motivation is responsible for defining human performance by energizing and guiding it. Getting students motivated could give them a path to achieving their goals. As, one of the fundamental aspects of being human is communication. English is the third most commonly used language in the world, according to Levis (Lewis, Simons, & Fennig, 2014). Therefore, English is crucial for connecting with individuals around the globe. According to Gardner (1985), one of the primary elements influencing English language learning has long been acknowledged to be the learner's motivation.

Key words: Motivation, EFL (English as a Foreign Language), communication, long-term goals, native speaker, language acquisition, instrumental and integrative motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, interjection, identification, and integration.

Annotatsiya: Til o'rganishda o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi juda muhimdir. EFL (Ingliz tili chet tili sifatida) talabalarini o'qib o'rganish jarayonida ishtirok etishga undash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Dornyei (1998) fikriga ko'ra, motivatsiya inson faoliyatini energiya bilan ta'minlash va boshqarish orqali aniqlash uchun javobgar. Talabalarni motivatsiya qilish ularga o'z maqsadlariga erishish yo'lini berishi mumkin. Insonning asosiy jihatlaridan biri bu muloqotdir. Levis (Lyuis, Simons va Fennig, 2014) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, ingliz tili dunyodagi uchinchi eng ko'p ishlatiladigan tildir. Shu sababli, ingliz tili butun dunyo bo'ylab odamlar bilan bog'lanish uchun juda muhimdir. Uzoq vaqt davomidan beri tan olinib kelingan Gardner (1985) fikriga ko'ra, ingliz tilini o'rganishga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy elementlardan biri o'quvchining motivatsiyasi ekanligi e'tirof etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Motivatsiya, EFL (Ingliz tili chet tili sifatida), muloqot, uzoq muddatli maqsadlar, ona tilida so'zlashuvchi, tilni o'zlashtirish, instrumental va integrativ motivatsiya, ichki va tashqi motivatsiya, undov, identifikatsiya va integratsiya.

Аннотация: Мотивация учащихся имеет решающее значение при изучении языка. Важно мотивировать студентов EFL (английский как иностранный язык) к участию в их обучении. Согласно Дорниеню (Dornyei, 1998), некоторые эксперты сходятся во мнении, что мотивация ответственна за определение эффективности человеческой деятельности, заряжая ее энергией и направляя ее. Мотивация студентов могла бы

указать им путь к достижению их целей. Одним из фундаментальных аспектов человеческого бытия является общение. По данным Левиса, английский является третьим наиболее часто используемым языком в мире (Lewis, Simons, & Fennig, 2014). Таким образом, английский язык имеет решающее значение для общения с людьми по всему миру. Согласно Гарднеру (1985), уже давно признано, что одним из основных элементов, влияющих на изучение английского языка, является мотивация учащегося.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, EFL (английский как иностранный язык), коммуникация, долгосрочные цели, носитель языка, овладение языком, инструментальная и интегративная мотивация, внутренняя и внешняя мотивация, междометие, идентификация и интеграция.

Introduction: One of the fundamental aspects of being human is communication. English is the third most commonly used language in the world, according to Levis (Lewis et al., 2014). Therefore, English is crucial for connecting with individuals around the globe. According to Gardner (1985), one of the most important elements influencing how well people acquire the English language is their motivation.

Due to their limited language expertise, particularly in terms of speaking and listening abilities, students who exhibit communication anxiety do not feel confident speaking in the target language in front of others. All students may not be able to speak in class since the environment can occasionally make it challenging for students to express and defend their thoughts. Their psychological state is affected, which makes them anxious when speaking in English. Their dread of speaking English, for instance, their fear of making blunders and mistakes, their fear of incorrect pronunciation, and their fear of using the incorrect tenses have become so imprinted in their memories that studying English is now difficult rather than enjoyable. Students eventually become demotivated as a result of situations like these. Motivation and pupils' anxiety when speaking English are tightly related. Even though they are speaking a language that is unfamiliar to them, they are uneasy, uneasy, and afraid. Anxiety should be suppressed because it will motivate you well. With strong positive motivation, they can increase their efforts to learn in order to achieve both short- and long-term goals (for instance, "I would like to work in foreign businesses that need employees to speak English"). In this instance, motivation and anxiety to learn a foreign language, particularly speaking English, do not appear to be isolated from the setting of language acquisition.

Motivation

Motivating EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students to participate in their learning is important. Some experts concur, according to Dornyei (1998), that motivation is responsible for defining human performance by energizing and guiding it. Engaging students' motivation may give them a path to realizing their goals.

Motivation, according to Gardner (R. C. Gardner et al., 1985), is "the extent to which the particular works or strives to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the approval experienced in the activity." This study aids in understanding why students are motivated to

learn English and assists the faculty in fostering that drive so that students can succeed in their studies.

Instrumental vs. Integrative Motivation

According to Gardner (1985, as stated in Kitjaroonchai, 2012), it was crucial to realize the students' ultimate aim or purpose for learning the language in order to fully appreciate why they were driven. This was his term for the student orientation. Two different placements acknowledged his notion of motivation for second language acquisition.

Instrumental Motivation

Students that have an instrumental motive aim to study a language for a variety of reasons, such as meeting work requirements or getting into college. Instrumental motivation as a technique of obtaining the social and financial gain through L2 Learning was measured by Gardner and Lambert in 1972. In order to study L2, motivation is essential. According to some researchers, a blend of integrative and instrumental motivation might influence students' drive to learn their target language. Additionally, Mun (2011) defines instrumental motivation as the desire to learn a language for more practical reasons, such as job search or social advancement.

There are three circumstances that are required for learning L2, for example:

- a) The requirement for eager students to pick up the target language.
- b) Assistance from a native speaker in learning L2.
- c) Conversations between students and a natural speaker of the target language.

Integrative Motivation

To syndicate the language with the student's target language is an integrated incentive. With integrative motivation, the students study the target language to better understand it, get to know native speakers, and immerse themselves in their culture. Integrative provocation, in the words of Gardner and Masgoret (2003), refers to "an openness to fete at least in part with another language community" (p. 126). Mun (2011) also defines integrative motivation as a motivation that lacks an outside enticement (reward). Due to the learners' positive behavior, an integrative motive drives them to study the foreign language. But the students want to fit in with the community speaking the target language.

Intrinsic vs. Extrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation is a drive that originates inside the person. They are motivated to learn the target language by a personal desire to do so. (Woolfolk, 1998) states that "intrinsic motivation is a motivation that stems from features such as interest or curiosity" (p. 374). In connection with that, intrinsic motivation may occur when a student is interested in studying English without feeling under any sort of obligation to do so.

Extrinsic motivation is inspiration that stems from the external environment. They are motivated to learn the target language by the challenges at work or school. Extrinsic motivation, according to Harmer (2007), is caused by external factors like the necessity to pass a test, the desire for financial gain, or the prospect of future travel. Additionally, Deci and Ryan (1985) put out 4 classifications for extrinsic incentive. Regulation from without, interjection, identification, and integration were these.

Wimolmas (2013) conducted a study in Thailand with the aim of identifying the instrumental and integrative motivations of English language learners. Undoubtedly, the researcher worked with 30 first-year undergraduate students from a global engineering and technology institute. His study's findings indicated that the students were generally quite motivated. The study revealed that the students were more motivated to learn English for practical purposes.

Rehman et al. (2014) presented a study to identify the function of motivation in Pakistani students' English language acquisition. 50 intermediate Pakistani students from a private college participated in the study. In terms of motivation, the findings showed that 70% of the students were more driven by practical reasons to study English. In addition, 6% of students did not provide their consent, and 24% of students wanted to learn English because they love the language. According to Oxford and Shearin (1994), who were referenced by Doryei (1998), "Quite possibly, the source of the motivation is quite significant in a practical sense to instructors who seek to foster learners' motivation. How can teachers water motivational roots if they are unaware of their locations?"

The teachers could be inspired by these statements to play their best part for the students. As a result, the students might be motivated to learn English more. Therefore, educators must focus on the students in order to teach and give the intrinsic motivation to the students in order to increase their proficiency in using English as a second language. According to Gardner (1985), the integrative-oriented pupils showed stronger persistence and motivation than other students. They demonstrated a significant desire to learn the language and had favorable opinions regarding both learning English and English-speaking individuals. Their aptitude for English would impact how well they learned and performed.

Conclusion

We may infer that the instrumental students' motivation was greater than that of the integrative students, indicating that the environment may have an impact on the students' drive to study English (Al-Bustan & Al-Bustan, 2009). Students may now understand the significance of learning English. Students believed that by learning English, they would be able to communicate with native English-speaking nations, land a good career in the future, and benefit from their ability to travel internationally.

The teachers and students who are teaching and learning English as a second language may find the following suggestions helpful. These recommendations should help teachers and students both learn English more effectively and teach EFL in a more effective manner. First, it is advised that students create goals, participate in activity groups, and demonstrate an enthusiasm in learning English. Next, recommendations for teachers include using activities and teaching strategies that encourage students' creativity and interest, such as assigning pairs of students to complete a project or using music or movies to teach EFL; fostering a cooperative classroom environment to lessen students' anxiety; and being proficient in both English and classroom management.

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